

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of α -(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines as Possible Antiamoebic Agents

M. P. Sreedharan and H. N. Sharma

Considering the formation of hypothetical degradation products of emetine due to the rupture of its molecule at various points, Kachru and Pathak¹ prepared α -(2-alkyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethylamines which were tested *in vitro* for amoebicidal activity by Kaushiva². The latter author found that the activity increased with alkylation, attaining the maximum value with alkyl as hexyl group. It is considered worthwhile to prepare some structural analogues and to examine their amoebicidal activity in order to locate the seat of activity in the amines. The present communication deals with the synthesis of α -(2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines with alkyl groups as propyl³, butyl⁴, and amyl⁵, which will be tested for their amoebicidal activity.

Procedure.—Acetoveratrone, prepared according to the method adopted by Pictet and Gams³, was converted into ethylveratrole by the Clemmensen reduction, following the procedure of Barger and Silverschmidt⁴. 2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl alkyl ketones were prepared in good yields by the Friedel-Crafts acylation according to the method described by Faragher and Perkin⁵ for acetomethylveratrone and Kachru and Pathak¹ for the preparation of 2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone. Ethylveratrole (0.2 *M*) was condensed with the corresponding acid chlorides (0.25 *M*) in CS₂ solution in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.5 *M*). Demethylation occurred profusely during acylation. Methylation was effected with dimethyl sulphate.

Only 2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl ethyl ketone, which solidified on cooling, was crystallised from gthanol, m.p. 48°. The Mannich base hydrochloride of the ketone with dimethylamine hydrochloride was prepared in the usual manner as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 196°. (Found: C, 4.40; Cl, 11.19. C₁₆H₂₆O₃NCl requires N, 4.43; Cl, 11.25%). The Mannich base hydrochloride of the same ketone with diethylamine hydrochloride melted at 222°. (Found: N, 4.12; Cl, 10.23. C₁₈H₃₀O₃NCl requires N, 4.08; Cl, 10.35%).

The ketones were converted into the corresponding oximes in the usual way, which separated as viscous oils, and could not be induced to solidify.

The oximes, as such, on subsequent reduction with metallic sodium and 'super dry'

1. *This Journal*, 1957, **34**, 768.
2. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **16C**, 224.
3. *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 2947.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2924.
5. *Ibid.*, 1921, **119**, 1724.

ethanol yielded the corresponding α -(2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines. The amines have been characterised as hydrochlorides.

TABLE I

2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl alkyl ketones.

R.	B.P.	2,4-D.N.P.		Phenylhydrazones.		
		Yield.	*M.P.	†M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.
Et	152-58°/2mm	87%	121°	136°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂	8.80 8.97
Pr ⁿ	143-47°/3	74	80°	108°	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	8.52 8.59
Bu ⁿ	160-62°/3	50	..	97°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂	8.20 8.24

*Crystallised from acetic acid.

†Crystallised from EtOH.

TABLE II

 α -(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines.

R.	B.P.	Hydrochloride.			Found.	Reqd.	Fiorate †M.P.
		Yield.	*M.P.	Formula.			
Et	130-40°/3mm	45.3	206°	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	N : 5.45 % Cl : 13.54	5.39 % 13.66	195°(d)
Pr ⁿ	160-65°/7	57.3	181°	C ₁₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	N : 5.10 Cl : 13.00	5.12 12.98	183°(d)
Bu ⁿ	165-75°/6	40.3	180°	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O ₂ NCl	N : 4.85 Cl : 12.34	4.90 12.35	178°(d)

*Crystallised from EtAc-absolute ethanol.

†Crystallised from dil. ethanol.

The various constants of the ketones and amines are recorded in Tables I and II respectively.

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Principal, Madhav College, Ujjain, for providing research facilities.